

EFFICACY OF APREMILAST IN MODERATE TO SEVERE PSORIASIS

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DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17586457>

Keywords

Efficacy; Apremilast; PASI,
Chronic plaque psoriasis

Article History

Received: 05 April, 2025

Accepted: 26 June, 2025

Published: 11 July, 2025

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Abstract

Background The lives of the patients may be considerably affected, particularly with moderately severe to severe psoriasis. This paper aims at evaluating the ability of apremilast in the management of patients having moderate to severe persistent plaque psoriasis.

Methods This study was a cross-sectional study conducted at the Dermatology Department of Pakistan Emirates Military Hospital during December 2023 to June 2024. Chronic plaque psoriasis patients between 18 and 60 years of age with Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) of 10 or higher were included in this study. Exclusion criteria encompassed patients with PASI scores under 10, comorbidities like eczema or systemic illnesses, and other specific conditions. The study enrolled 146 patients who received Apremilast, a phosphodiesterase 4 inhibitor, for 12 weeks. Efficacy was assessed based on a 75% or greater reduction in PASI scores. Data analysis was done using IBM-SPSS 21.0 and the statistically significant level set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results 146 patients with moderate to severe psoriasis, ages 18 to 60, were enrolled in the study. Their mean age was 40.2 ± 11.7 years. There were 43.8% of men ($n = 64$) and 56.2% of women ($n = 82$) in the cohort. Efficacy, defined as a significant reduction in PASI score, was achieved in 55.5% ($n = 81$) of patients, while 44.5% ($n = 65$) did not reach the desired outcome. Baseline mean PASI score was 25.4 ± 8.5 , decreasing significantly to 13.1 ± 4.8 after 12 weeks ($p = 0.001$).

Conclusion Apremilast was found to be effective in treating moderate to severe psoriasis, and its safety profile aligned with the established guidelines.

INTRODUCTION

Papulosquamous lesions are a hallmark of psoriasis, a persistent, proliferative, and inflammatory skin disorder. This is known to be, predominantly, autoimmune and most often manifests in the extensor surfaces as well as scalp. Palmoplantar psoriasis may be localized, affecting only palms and soles or may be

combined with other forms and involve almost all parts of-body or only a few localized plaques. According to different population studies, psoriasis is found to be uniformly distributed in Europe and the United States with a prevalence of between 2% and 3% while a research completed in Asia showed a

prevalence of 0.47% [1, 2]. The etiology of psoriasis is believed to be partly heritable with some other factors arising from the environment, whereas its mechanism of development remains unknown [3]. Besides being closely associated with the skin and joint diseases, psoriasis is found to be associated with cancer and with various systemic diseases such as cardiac, hepatic, and gastrointestinal diseases [4]. The point concerning stress is one of the most observable facts, as it is established that both psychic and emotional stress may act as the trigger for the development of psoriasis. Additionally, stress can worsen the symptoms of the disease [4]. There are topical as well as systemic treatments for patients suffering from psoriasis. Some of the common topical treatments include corticosteroid, dithranol, vitamin D analogues, salicylic acid and phototherapy. salicylic acid, and phototherapy are examples of frequently used topical therapies. Further, biological agents are cyclosporine, methotrexate, and retinoids can be classified as systemic treatment [5].

A recently developed drug named apremilast acts upon the phosphodiesterase-4 (PDE4) enzyme to increase the cyclic AMP (cAMP) concentration and the inflammatory response responsible for psoriasis. The United States Food and Drug Administration (FDA) endorsed Apremilast in 2014 for patients with moderate to serious persistent plaque psoriasis to be treated with phototherapy or systemic therapy only [6]. In the current armory of drugs used to manage psoriasis, attention has been given to Apremilast more so because of its immunomodulating effect [7, 8].

In a clinical study, 43.3% of patients who received apremilast achieved PASI-75, which means improvement by at least 75% for a patient compared with baseline [9]. In another study, 81% of the patients who took apremilast achieved similar level of PASI-75 [10]. Additionally, in a separate study, the baseline PASI score for patients on apremilast was 11.9 ± 2.8 , which decreased to 7.9 ± 3.4 after three months of follow-up. 28.5% of patients receiving apremilast showed a decrease of $\geq 75\%$ from baseline (PASI-75) [11].

The quality of life is significantly impacted by psoriasis, and reducing functional impairment requires early diagnosis and treatment. Although various studies have been conducted globally with differing outcomes, there has been no such study in

our specific setting until now. Thus, the objective of this research was to evaluate apremilast's efficacy in treating individuals with moderate to severe chronic plaque psoriasis.

Methods

A cross-sectional study was conducted in the Dermatology Department of Pakistan Emirates Military Hospital over a six-month period from December 2023 to June 2024. The study included patients aged 18 to 60 years, of both sexes, who had chronic plaque psoriasis of any duration with a Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) score of 10 or greater. Patients were excluded if they presented with erythematous, scaly, indurated lesions with a PASI score of less than 10 or had comorbidities such as lichen planus, eczema, or systemic illnesses like chronic lung disease, liver disease, or anemia. Additionally, patients who were alcoholics, had drug allergies, a BMI less than 18, pustular, erythrodermic, or psoriatic arthritis, or were pregnant or lactating, or had Hepatitis B, Hepatitis C, or HIV, were also excluded.

146 patients who satisfied the inclusion criteria were enrolled in the trial. Following counselling of the treatment's advantages and possible drawbacks, all subjects gave their medical approval. Group A received a 30 mg tablet of the phosphodiesterase 4 inhibitor apremilast, which was taken twice daily starting on day 6 and continuing for 12 weeks. By calculating the reduction in the PASI score at baseline and at the end of the 12-week treatment period, the effectiveness of Apremilast was evaluated. If the PASI score reduced from baseline by 75% or more, the medication was considered effective. The effectiveness of Apremilast was the main focus of the study, as evidenced by the decrease in the PASI score from the beginning to the end of the 12-week period. If the PASI score reduced by 75% or more, the medication was considered effective.

IBM-SPSS 21.0 was then used to validate, code, and analyse the study's data. Means, standard deviations, ranges, medians, and percentages were among the descriptive statistics that were computed. For continuous variables, a paired t-test was used to compare the PASI score at baseline and twelve weeks later. Statistical significance was determined at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results

146 patients with moderate to severe psoriasis, ages 18 to 60, were enrolled in the study. Their mean age was 40.2 ± 11.7 years. There were 43.8% of men (n = 64) and 56.2% of women (n = 82) in the cohort. Participants had psoriasis for an average of 6.2 ± 2.9 months, with a range of 2 to 9 months. Family history of psoriasis was reported in 45.9% (n = 67) of the patients, while 54.1% (n = 79) had no family history.

The mean body surface area affected by psoriasis was 7.5 ± 3.6 , with a range of 4 to 15. The baseline Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) score averaged 25.4 ± 8.5 , which reduced to 13.1 ± 4.8 after 12 weeks of treatment. Efficacy, defined as a significant reduction in the PASI score, was achieved in 55.5% (n = 81) of the patients, while 44.5% (n = 65) did not achieve the desired therapeutic outcome as shown in Table 1.

Table 1 Demographical characteristics and clinical parameters with moderate to severe psoriasis.

Variables	Categories	Total (N = 146)
Age (years)	Mean \pm SD*	40.2 ± 11.7
	Minimum-Maximum	40 (18-60)
Sex	Female	82 (56.2)
	Male	64 (43.8)
Duration (months)	Mean \pm SD*	6.2 ± 2.9
	Minimum-Maximum	6 (2-9)
Family history	Absent	79 (54.1)
	Present	67 (45.9)
Psoriasis-involved body surface area	Mean \pm SD*	7.5 ± 3.6
	Minimum-Maximum	8 (4-15)
Psoriasis area and severity index (baseline)	Mean \pm SD*	25.4 ± 8.5
	Mean \pm SD*	13.1 ± 4.8
Psoriasis area and severity index (12 weeks)	Mean \pm SD*	13.1 ± 4.8
	Not achieved	65 (44.5)
Efficacy	Achieved	81 (55.5)

SD (standard deviation).

Table 2 demonstrates the baseline and 12-week treatment Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) ratings of patients with moderate to severe psoriasis. At baseline, the mean PASI score was 25.4 ± 8.5 implying that the disease was of relatively high severity. Mean PASI score decreased to 13.1 ± 4.8 at

the end of 12 weeks of the treatment regime. The PASI score differences being statistically significant at a $p < 0.001$ it can be concluded that the treatment was effective in reducing the psoriasis severity in the study population. The reduced values of PASI indicate a relevant clinical improvement in the condition of the patients throughout the course of the study.

Table 2 Bifurcation of Psoriasis area and severity index (PASI) at baseline and after 12 weeks in patients with moderate to severe psoriasis.

Variables	Categories	PASI At baseline	PASI After 12 weeks	p-value
Psoriasis area and severity index				0.001
	Mean \pm SD*	25.4 ± 8.5	13.1 ± 4.8	

SD (standard deviation)

The safety profile of 146 patients diagnosed with moderate to severe psoriasis was assessed based on the occurrence of various adverse events. Diarrhea was reported in 16.4% (n = 24) of the patients, while the majority, 83.6% (n = 122), did not experience this side effect. Nausea was present in 13.1% (n = 19) of the patients, with 86.9% (n = 127) not reporting this symptom. Headache occurred in 10.3% (n = 15) of the patients, whereas 89.7% (n = 131) were unaffected. Stomatitis was observed in 7.5% (n = 11) of the

patients, and the remaining 92.5% (n = 135) did not develop this condition. Infections were reported in 6.2% (n = 9) of the patients, while 93.8% (n = 137) did not experience any infections. Finally, only 2.1% (n = 3) of the patients had deranged liver function tests (LFTs), with 97.9% (n = 143) showing no liver function abnormalities as shown in Table 3. Overall, the majority of patients tolerated the treatment well, with relatively few experiencing significant adverse effects.

Table 3 Safety profile of all the patients diagnosed with moderate to severe psoriasis.

Variables	Categories	Total (N = 146)
Diarrhea	Absent	122 (83.6)
	Present	24 (16.4)
Nausea	Absent	127 (86.9)
	Present	19 (13.1)
Headache	Absent	131 (89.7)
	Present	15 (10.3)
Stomatitis	Absent	135 (92.5)
	Present	11 (7.5)
Infection	Absent	137 (93.8)
	Present	9 (6.2)
Deranged LFTs	Absent	143 (97.9)
	Present	3 (2.1)

Discussion

Psoriasis is a prevalent chronic condition that is genetically determined and marked by remission and recurrence intervals. The condition significantly impacts the quality of life due to the associated morbidity. Each new treatment option represents a valuable advancement for patients with psoriasis. There are several therapy modalities available, such as systemic therapies for moderate to severe disease and topical treatments for mild cases. Methotrexate, cyclosporine, acitretin, apremilast, biologic medicines

(e.g., etanercept, secukinumab, and infliximab), and phototherapy are examples of systemic alternatives. Combination therapy is also employed, tailored to the disease severity, efficacy, side effect profiles, patient quality of life, and affordability, with both short- and long-term considerations taken into account [12]. Our study demonstrated that apremilast was effective, as indicated by the reduction in Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) scores following the initiation of treatment. Apremilast was determined to be a better course of treatment after 12 weeks, with a

greater percentage of patients experiencing notable clinical improvement.

The median age in our study was 40 (18–60) years, and the mean was 40.2 ± 11.7 . On the other hand, an average age of 12 years was recorded in a research by Lomholt [13]. While study from the UK showed a mean onset age of 33 years, with 75% of patients getting psoriasis before the age of 46 [15], extensive surveys carried out in the United States revealed that the average age of onset was 28 years [14]. Furthermore, a bimodal age distribution was found in a German study, with an early onset between the ages of 16 and 22 and a later onset between the ages of 57 and 60 [16]. Additionally, Khalid, Amna, et al.'s study in Pakistan found that patients receiving apremilast had an average age of 40.22 ± 11.81 years [17].

Our study population comprised 82 females (56.2%) and 64 males (43.8%). The higher proportion of females in our cohort may be attributed to greater feelings of stigmatization and psychological impact associated with the disease among women. Research indicates that women with psoriasis experience more severe psychological distress compared to men: they report higher levels of unhappiness (18.5% vs. 11.3% lower than the general population), stress (over 60% vs. 42%), social isolation (25-28% vs. 19-24%), stigmatization (Feelings of Stigmatization Questionnaire score: 93.2 vs. 78.0), and reduced libido (33% vs. 19%) [18]. Consequently, more women may seek treatment for psoriasis [20]. Similarly, a study by Gawlik et al. found that 56.92% (70 out of 130) of patients were female, which aligns closely with our findings [19]. In contrast, other studies have reported a higher prevalence of psoriasis among males, such as in Germany (0.76% vs. 0.66%) and the United States (2.5% vs. 1.9%, with an odds ratio of 1.37; 95% CI: 1.14–1.64 [20, 21].

In our study, patients in the apremilast group had a mean Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) score of 25.4 ± 8.5 at baseline. By the end of 12 weeks, the mean PASI score had decreased to 13.1 ± 4.8 . Apremilast, an oral phosphodiesterase-4 (PDE4) inhibitor, works by increasing levels of cyclic adenosine monophosphate (cAMP), which reduces pro-inflammatory cytokines and enhances anti-inflammatory cytokines, thus improving psoriasis-associated inflammation [22, 23]. According to Phase III double-blind trials (Esteem 1 and 2), apremilast has

demonstrated both safety and efficacy in treating moderate to severe plaque psoriasis, including in patients with various comorbidities [24]. These trials indicated that a 30 mg twice-daily dosage of apremilast resulted in PASI response rates ranging from 29% to 41% [24]. Additionally, one study reported that 43.3% of patients achieved a 75% or greater reduction from baseline PASI score (PASI-75) [9], while another study observed a PASI-75 response in 81% of patients treated with apremilast [10].

81 patients (55.5%) in the apremilast group in our trial experienced effectiveness, which is defined as a 75% or higher decrease in the Psoriasis Area and Severity Index (PASI) score in comparison to baseline. The baseline PASI scores for apremilast and methotrexate were 11.9 ± 2.8 and 11.9 ± 2.8 , respectively, in a different trial. The apremilast group's PASI score dropped to 7.9 ± 3.4 after a 3-month follow-up. In contrast to 85.9% of individuals receiving methotrexate, 28.5% of patients receiving apremilast experienced a $\geq 75\%$ reduction from baseline PASI (PASI-75) [25]. According to the current study, patients with moderate to severe psoriasis can benefit from apremilast as a systemic treatment option. Although randomised clinical trials have demonstrated the effectiveness and tolerability of topical treatments for mild-to-moderate psoriasis, guidelines advise taking systemic therapies into consideration for patients who have a high disease burden or insufficient control with topical treatments, including those whose psoriasis affects specific areas. The lack of an active-comparator arm limits the study's capacity to directly compare this medication to other systemic therapies. Furthermore, the findings' applicability to larger clinical contexts may be constrained by the study population's homogeneity. To improve their applicability, real-world data should be added to these findings.

Conclusion

Psoriasis is a recurring, chronic skin condition that has a major negative impact on one's quality of life. There are numerous therapy approaches for treating this medical condition. It has been demonstrated that apremilast considerably and clinically meaningfully reduces the severity of psoriasis overall. In people with moderate to severe psoriasis, it also improves quality

of life and symptoms like whole-body itching and scalp psoriasis.

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